

Education Is The Pillar of A Nation

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Abstract

Education is an essential part of any nation to understand its culture and society. Now a days, education is the part of life where we prove ourselves. It is not a part of academic experience but also a part of every movement which we face in the society. Education is very important for all the people because it reminds us of the importance of life. It focuses on the behaviour of everyone who belongs to any society. Its aim is to make people self dependent. It plays an important role in the development of women empowerment. Today, women empowerment is the chief movement of the society. The women of the society have understood their rights by getting education. An Indian popular writer, *AMISH TRIPATHI* (1974) has focused on women empowerment in his works. In his writings we find that women play an important role in the society. In his *Shiva Trilogy*, he has proved that women are not inferior to men, they have equal rights to get education.

Keywords

Education, Child Development, Women Empowerment, Freedom, Nationalism.

Introduction

Education is the transmission of knowledge. It plays an important role in everyone's life. It is the pillar of a nation which develops the life of people. *JOHN DEWY*, (1859-1952) a philosopher rightly said, "**Education is not preparation of life ;Education is life itself.**"

It is the process of acquiring knowledge and skills. It builds morals, values and develops habits in people's mind. It is true that the process of education can be said to be complete only if you are able to put the knowledge you acquire to good use. According to *ALBERT EINSTEIN* (1879-1955)

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to discuss about the importance of Education in human life.

Review of Literature

"Education is not the learning of facts, but the training of the mind to think."

No doubt, the aim of education should be action and not just knowledge. It makes everyone a better person and gives him stability in life. The purpose of education is to make people perfect in their life. According to *BENJAMIN FRANKLIN* (1706-1790)

"An investment in knowledge pays the best interest."

The importance of education in students' life create opportunities for acquiring knowledge and skills that are literally changing the world. Every student should be eager to gain knowledge from everywhere. The purpose of their study is to develop critical thinking and problem solving skills. Their success greatly depends on their level of study. An essayist *FRANCIS BACON* (1561-1626) rightly said in his essay '**OF STUDIES**' (1597),

"Studies serve for delight, for ornament, and for ability."

In fact, education is the most effective means of preventing intolerance. It encourages students to tackle challenges of their life. According to *ARISTOTLE* (384BC-322BC),

"The roots of education are bitter, but the fruit is sweet."

It can be said that taking education seriously is not just an important decision for a student, but also it is a socially responsible behaviour. In this way it can be said that education is crucial for the development of both the individual and the entire society. A person's education plays an important role in their lives. Through education, we not only acquire new knowledge but also pass on knowledge from earlier generation to the present. *G.K.CHESTERTON* (1874-1936) said,

Main Text

"Education is simply the soul of a society as it passess from one generation to another."

Education makes us better person and helps to develop our overall personality. It also helps us to become a good citizen of our nation. It helps us to change the world. It works like a weapon. *NELSON MANDELA (1918-2013)*, The president of South Africa rightly said,

“Education is the most potent weapon which you can use to change the world.”

It is true that education is the pillar of a nation. The people of a nation have different ideas which help them to take any decision and all these things are possible only by education. In reference to women it also plays an important role to develop their ideas and they aware about their rights. Education is the backbone of women empowerment.

Today, women empowerment is the most important topic of a nation. The educated women can fight for their rights. In ancient time women have no proper rights in the society. They were not aware of education. A British poet, *ALFRED LORD TENNYSON (1809-1892)*, wrote in his poem ‘**THE PRINCESS**’ (1847)

“Man for the field and woman for the hearth;

Man for the sword, and for the needle she;

Man with the head, and woman with the heart;

Man to command, and woman to obey;

All else confusion.”

The condition of women was not good in ancient time. Women suffered a lot in every country. But now women are the pillar of every nation and they encourage the society in every field. No doubt, education is the boon for women who are well settled in the society.

The significance of education cannot be emphasised enough. Education moulds individuals into improved, better-informed and accountable members of society. It also plays a significant role in the socialisation of children by introducing them to moral values. Education has an important influence on socialisation process by developing the intellectual practice of the students.

Conclusion

No doubt, education is the pillar of a nation because it reflects whole nation. It is true that every nation can be strong only through education. It is an essential part of every nation because no nation can progress without education. So it is the backbone of every nation. It helps to develop moral values in the heart of citizen. The government of every nation should be helpful in the development of education. At last we can say that education is a powerful weapon for economic and cultural change in a society. An educated society can present its country to the world, that is education works to increase social capacity.

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